

WAYS TO DEVELOP THE SYSTEM OF CAR MAINTENANCE AND REPAIR IN OUR COUNTRY

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Abstract: This article presents the content, essence, history of the car maintenance and repair system, its role in the country's economy, and ways to develop this industry using foreign experiences.

Key words: Economy, service sector, development, foreign experience, motor transport services, public transport service, cargo delivery service, services marketing, transport service, technical service, country's economy.

Introduction: It is known from the world practice that today it is possible to get more income in the short term while spending less in the service sector. In particular, today several areas of the service sector, including communication and information, finance, transport, construction, tourism and trade services, can be cited as an example.

Service delivery is a configuration of technology and organizational networks designed to provide services that satisfy the needs, demands, or aspirations of customers. Many literatures refer to the management of service as service operations, service marketing, service engineering, and service design. Although this term appears frequently, it is rarely used.

One of the most common types of services today is a transport service which occupies an important place in our lives. Transport service, which is the lifeblood of our economy, is a type of service to the population in these cars. Transportation is used more than other types of transport service. As a population depends on moving from A place to the B, this mean of service is used to get people to their destinations, not to mention transportation of their goods.

In turn, after a certain period of time, in the cases when a malfunction is detected in the vehicle, the technical service branches of motor vehicles are contacted. Car maintenance system is also important.

Analysis of literature on the topic (Literature review)

In the scientific-methodological issues of the effective development of the car maintenance system, it was studied by foreign scientists Ye.S.Kuznetsova, G.V.Kramarenko, V.Barashkov, L.L.Afanasev, V.V. , Markeev, V.A. Akopov, Y.I. Borovskikh and many others.. In the study of these problems, among the Uzbek

scientists M.Q. many current issues such as effective organization, management, development of the display and repair system are covered in his scientific works.

Research methodology

Conclusions and proposals were formed as a result of the analysis of the indicators of the development of the automobile service sector through economic-mathematical methods during the implementation of the research. In addition, the method of analysis and synthesis was effectively used in the implementation of scientific research.

Analysis and results

One of the priorities of the social policy in our country is increasing the income of the population and their standards of living through the development of small businesses and private entrepreneurships. A number of facilities are provided in the field of services for the population to live more comfortable, not having any social problems. As a result, thanks to the development of service infrastructure in our country the way of life of the population is improving.

In developed countries, there are more than 30,000 types of services, including transport services. Today, transport services are utilized in air, sea, rail and road services. For instance, road transport is used to convey the most passengers and goods around the world or a vehicle service is a special type of privilege designed for the transportation of weapons, fuel, and food.

Cars are one of the important technical means of modern human life and culture. The importance of cars in the development of the country's economy and culture, ensuring its safety and meeting the population's demand for transportation is incomparable. At the same time, it is important to ensure the safety of passengers transported by cars and the complete arrival of goods to the destination by bus.

In such cases, it is important to carry out a technical inspection of cars. This is needed for reducing the risk of emergency accidents, ensuring the safety of people in any type of transportation. As for the definitions of car maintenance, they are covered differently in many literatures:

In most cases, vehicle maintenance or tune-ups are conservation procedures performed at specified intervals or after the vehicle has traveled a certain distance. Service intervals are specified by the car manufacturer in the service schedule, and while some modern cars are said to display the next service date electronically on the instrument panel, some literature states that Maintenance – is a set of measures taken to extend the period of utilization of cars.

These activities are carried out in order to ensure that the cars work with the standard efficiency, requiring maintenance of all existing vehicles. Both used and maintained vehicles will need conservation. It is planned that the uniform maintenance standards for motor vehicles will be established. Technical service is divided into two types such as prevention (prophylaxis) and restoration (correction, repair).

(Figure 1).

Figure 1. Car maintenance

Technical service activities can be carried out in specially equipped workshops at the place where the vehicle is parked. In both cases, the necessary weapons, tools, and materials are primarily required to be qualified specialists (plumbers, electricians, engine repairmen, welders, vulcanizers (balloon patchers), etc.). Today, specialists who repair motor vehicles are called auto mechanics. Car mechanic - a specialist who performs the repair and maintenance of motor vehicles, as well as monitoring the technical condition of cars using diagnostic equipment and tools. For example, a dynamometer, a car scanner, etc. The costs of using motor vehicles are reduced, their technical capabilities are increased, and their service life is extended.

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